

α -Naphthol does not condense in presence of sulphuric acid. This is analogous to the similar behaviour of α -naphthol with α -benzyl acetoacetate (Naik, Desai and Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 801). Orcinol and phloroglucinol in presence of sulphuric acid give products from which no crystalline substance could be obtained. When sulphuric acid is replaced by phosphorus oxychloride as a condensing agent, the corresponding coumarins are obtained in good yield. In all cases, the condensation in presence of oxychloride proceeds easily at ordinary temperature even without a solvent.

To prove the coumarin structure, the condensation product, derived from resorcinol, has been subjected to hydrolysis and methylation according to the method of Canter and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1875). Due to the complications arising on account of the hydrolysis of $-\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_2$ group, no definite product is obtained. The condensation product is first reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid (Meldrum and Alimchandani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 1). The Canter-Robertson method fails to convert the reduction product into its *o*-methoxy-cinnamic acid, which is easily obtained according to the modified method of Shah and Shah (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, 213); the acid on oxidation gives 2:4-dimethoxyacetophenone, identical with an authentic specimen. The condensation product of pyrogallol has been similarly treated and the corresponding cinnamic acid obtained.

To study the effect of the change of the condensing agent on the above reaction, phosphorus pentoxide (Simonis' reaction) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228) have

been tried. Resorcinol and phloroglucinol with phosphorus pentoxide as condensing agent give a poor yield of the respective coumarins identical with the products obtained above. Pyrogallol, α -naphthol and orcinol do not condense at all (*cf.* Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 407). Anhydrous aluminium chloride is found to be unsatisfactory as no product could be isolated. This may be due to the complications arising on account of its side reactions on $\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_2$ group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

7-Hydroxy-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-4-methylcoumarin.— To a well cooled mixture of resorcinol (3 g.) and ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate (7.5 g.), sulphuric acid (78%; 30 c.c.) was added in small instalments, the mixture being well shaken after each addition. The colour of the solution gradually changed to deep brown on keeping. After 4 hours, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice in thin stream. A yellow semi-solid mass separated; it was repeatedly washed with water and dried. It was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from chloroform as tiny rhombic plates, m.p. $207\text{--}8^\circ$ (decomp.), yield 1 g. (Found: Cl, 33.09. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 32.90 per cent).

The coumarin is easily soluble in alcohol and acetone, difficultly so in chloroform, acetic acid, ethyl acetate and toluene. In alkaline solution, it exhibits blue fluorescence characteristic of a 7-hydroxycoumarin. Alcoholic ferric chloride gives green colour.

The above condensation was studied in presence of (i) phosphorus oxychloride, (ii) phosphorus pentoxide and (iii) aluminium chloride: (i) To a mixture of resorcinol (2 g.) and ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate (5 g.), phosphorus oxychloride (4 c.c.) was slowly added with shaking and cooling; the clear solution was allowed to stand for 12 hours and worked up by adding into water; the solid crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. $207\text{--}8^\circ$ (decomp.) (mixed m.p. with the specimen obtained above), yield nearly 2 g. (iii) The above condensation was repeated with phosphorus pentoxide (10 g.); the mixture was left overnight and after addition of more phosphorus pentoxide (5 g.), was heated on a water-bath for nearly 10 minutes. The oily product obtained was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide, filtered and acidified; the solid obtained on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 206° (mixed m.p. with an authentic coumarin), the yield was poor. (iii) The usual procedure of Sethna, Shah and Shah (*loc. cit.*) was adopted, but no definite product was obtained.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid, crystallised from rectified spirit as rectangular plates, m.p. 149-50°. (Found: Cl, 25.89. $C_{16}H_{13}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 26.12 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared by dimethyl sulphate and alkali (2%) in the cold, separated out slowly and was crystallised from dilute alcohol as plates, m.p. 154-55°. (Found: Cl, 30.17. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30.27 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative, obtained by benzoyl chloride and pyridine in cold, crystallised from alcohol as tiny plates, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: Cl, 24.72. $C_{19}H_{15}O_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24.9 per cent). In order to get a dibenzoyl derivative, the benzoylation was tried at a higher temperature; a pasty mass was obtained which could not be crystallised.

7-Hydroxy-3-(β-chlorovinyl)-4-methylcoumarin.—7-Hydroxy-3-(α-hydroxy-βββ-trichloroethyl)-4-methylcoumarin (2 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.). Zinc dust (2 g.) was added in small quantities with stirring. After the reaction was over, the solution was boiled for a few minutes, filtered from unchanged zinc and the filtrate diluted with water, when a solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 254-55° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.28; H, 3.99; Cl, 14.74. $C_{12}H_8O_3Cl$ requires C, 60.90; H, 3.83; Cl, 14.97 per cent). An alcoholic solution of the substance exhibits blue fluorescence.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride and pyridine, crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 169-170°. (Found: Cl, 12.6. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.73 per cent).

2:4-Dimethoxy-β-methyl-α-(β-chlorovinyl)-cinnamic Acid.—Dimethyl sulphate (10 c.c.) was first added to a warm solution of the reduction product (1.5 g.) in acetone (20 c.c.). Potassium hydroxide (20% ; 50 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for about 1½ hours. Some more dimethyl sulphate and alkali were added at intervals. The mixture was cooled, acidified and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5% ; 100 c.c.) and the bicarbonate layer acidified; the precipitated acid was crystallised from water in small plates and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 172-73°. (Found: Cl, 12.37. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.54 per cent).

The *silver salt* was prepared and analysed. (Found: Ag, 27.55. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4ClAg$ requires Ag, 27.7 per cent).

The *cinnamic acid* (1.5 g.) was dissolved in hot acetone (70 c.c.) and aqueous permanganate (2% ; 320 c.c.) added in small instalments, the

temperature being maintained at 45-50°. When the oxidation was complete, sulphur dioxide was passed and the clear solution extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and dried over calcium chloride. On removal of ether, a semi-solid residue was obtained, which was characterised by the preparation of its semicarbazone, which was found identical with the semicarbazone prepared from 2:4-dimethoxyacetophenone, m.p. 202° (mixed m.p.).

7:8-Dihydroxy-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-4-methylcoumarin. — Sulphuric acid (78%; 25 c.c.) was added in small quantities to a well cooled mixture of pyrogallol (3 g.) and the ester (6.6 g.) with thorough shaking. After 4 hours, the reaction mixture was worked up as before; the product crystallised from acetic acid and then from ethyl acetate as rhombic flakes, m.p. 223° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: Cl, 31.1. $C_{12}H_9O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 31.35 per cent). The coumarin is easily soluble in alcohol and acetone, difficultly so in acetic acid, ethyl acetate; insoluble in benzene and chloroform. It dissolves in alkali with orange colour; alcoholic ferric chloride gives green colour.

The above condensation was tried in presence of the following condens-
ing agents:

(a) To a well cooled mixture of pyrogallol and ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate in the same proportions as above, phosphorus oxychloride (4 c.c.) was added slowly with shaking. The clear solution was left aside for 12 hours and worked up as in case of resorcinol. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 223° (mixed m.p. with the coumarin obtained above). The yield was almost quantitative.

(b) The above condensation could not be effected in presence of phosphorus pentoxide.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol in hexagonal plates, m.p. 181°. (Found: Cl, 22.55. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 22.86 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as before, crystallised from dilute alcohol in prisms, m.p. 139°. (Found: Cl, 28.16. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 27.88 per cent).

7:8-Dihydroxy-3-(β -chlorovinyl)-4-methylcoumarin.—The condensation product (2.2 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (30 c.c.), was treated with zinc dust (2 g.) as before. After the reaction was over, unchanged zinc was filtered off and the filtrate diluted with water. The reduction product was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol as needles, m.p. 231-32° (decomp.). (Found: C, 57.29; H, 3.74; Cl, 14.24. $C_{11}H_9O_4Cl$ requires C, 57.07; H, 3.59; Cl, 14.04 per cent).

2:3:4-Trimethoxy- β -methyl- α -(β -chlorovinyl)-cinnamic Acid.—The reduction product (1.2 g.) in its acetone solution (15 c.c.) was treated with dimethyl sulphate (10 c.c.) and potassium hydroxide solution (20% ; 50 c.c.) on a hot water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, as in case of resorcinol. The acid was isolated as before and crystallised from water and recrystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether, m.p. 125-26°. Its silver salt was analysed. (Found: Ag, 25.44. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6ClAg$ requires Ag, 25.74 per cent).

4-Methyl-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-1:2- α -naphthapyrone.—Phosphorus oxychloride (2 c.c.) was added to a well cooled mixture of α -naphthol (4 g.) and the ester (8 g.) and the mixture left for 40 hours at room temperature. It was then poured into water, the solid well washed with water and crystallised from alcohol and recrystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 231-32°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: Cl, 29.84. $C_{18}H_{11}O_2Cl_3$ requires Cl, 29.76 per cent).

The coumarin dissolves sparingly in alkali; in alcoholic solution it exhibits a violet fluorescence; it gives no ferric reaction.

The acetyl derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride and pyridine, crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetone as prisms, m.p. 207-8°. (Found: Cl, 26.7. $C_{18}H_{13}O_4Cl_3$ requires Cl, 26.62 per cent).

5-Hydroxy-4:7-dimethyl-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-coumarin.—To a mixture of orcinol (4 g.) and the ester (9 g.), phosphorus oxychloride (3 c.c.) was gradually added and the mixture left for 40 hours. On working up as before, the substance obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 223-24° (decomp.), yield 3 g. (Found: Cl, 31.77. $C_{18}H_{11}O_4Cl_3$ requires Cl, 31.51 per cent). The coumarin dissolves in alkali with a non-fluorescent deep yellow colour.

5:7-Dihydroxy-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-4-methylcoumarin.—Phloroglucinol (4 g.) and the ester (9 g.) were treated with phosphorus oxychloride (5 c.c.) and the mixture left for 2 days. It was worked up as in the previous cases. The product crystallised from alcohol and was recrystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum benzene as thin rhombic plates, m.p. 216-17°, yield 3 g. (Found: Cl, 31.12. $C_{18}H_9O_5Cl_3$ requires Cl, 31.33 per cent). The coumarin exhibits violet fluorescence in alcoholic solution and dissolves in alkali with a greenish colour.

This condensation was carried up in presence of phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) with the reactants in the same proportions as before. Alcohol (3 c.c.) was added as solvent (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 410). The mixture was kept for 3 days at room temperature; water was then carefully added and the solution extracted with ether. On removal of

ether the product was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 216° (mixed m.p. with the above product). The yield was very poor.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride in pyridine, crystallised from dilute acetic acid and then from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether, m.p. $147-48^{\circ}$. (Found : Cl, 22.84. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 22.86 per cent).

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